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PreMETS

**Predictive Maintenance Education & Training System:
An alliance for boosting the European Innovation in
Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial
cooperation, education, and training**

Project Acronym: **PreMETS**

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D1.1 Project Management Plan

Final

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Abbreviations and Terminology

Abbreviations	
AB	Advisory Board
DG	Dissemination Group
EC	European Commission
MC	Management Committee
PC	Project Coordinator
PM	Project Manager
PO	Project Officer
QCP	Quality Control Panel
QM	Quality Manager
StC	Steering Committee
TL	Task Leader
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Terminology	
Conformity	The fulfilment of a specified requirement by a quality characteristic of an item or service, the assessment of which does not depend essentially on time.
Quality system	The organizational structure, responsibilities, activities, resources and events that together provide organized procedures and methods of implementation to ensure the capability of the Partner / Consortium to meet quality requirements.
Quality	The totality of features and characteristics of a prototype or service that bear on its ability to satisfy a given need.

Executive Summary

This document presents the Project Management Plan of PreMETS that complements the project information provided in the Grant Agreement and Description of Action, integrating more detailed procedures.

The main objective of Deliverable 1.1 is to establish and maintain a quality control program to be followed by project partners throughout the course of the project. The manual sets directions, practices and strategies for ensuring high quality performance of the project deliverables and undertakings.

The Plan specifies the activities that need to be implemented, including their sequence, in order to ensure that the project and its deliverables fully conform to the objectives that have been set. The Plan is to be used by:

- The consortium partners that will be responsible for monitoring the project activities.
- The consortium partners that will be responsible for preparing and amending the project's deliverables.
- The consortium partners that will be responsible for reviewing and approving specific activities to be undertaken for completing the respective project's deliverables.

The main components of the "Project Management Plan" can be summarized to the following:

- Project Management structure
- Quality plan procedure
- Quality Evaluation
- Documentation control procedures (templates, layout, coding, etc.)
- Strategies for the project internal communication
- Risk mitigation

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Purpose of the document

The main objective of this document is to make the cooperation among PREMETS partners easier and more efficient, giving a complete guideline with all information, rules and procedures so that the scientific outcomes comply with the PREMETS project's work plan and contractual obligations and results fulfil the technical requirements set by the PREMETS Consortium for effective progress toward the achievement of the project goals.

The PREMETS Management Plan is based on several principles that are important in inter-organizational collaboration:

1. An effective Project Management relies on the collaboration and cooperation among partners. The PREMETS partners are collaborating to achieve a common objective, share experience and know-how, and develop results with complementary skills;
2. Work must be organised and planned in a result-driven way. While the internal organisation of each partner's work depends on him/her (as long as he meets his/her commitments), the interactions between partners working at distance must be based on the flow of results. Common planning must hence be a reference for everybody and must always be up-to-date;
3. The collaboration between partners is based on consensus and joint decision-making, involving different levels of decision-makers in different domains (strategic, technical, financial, and administrative). The decisions will be achieved by "rough consensus and running code (or experiments)", using formal procedures such as voting only when essential. The rules for such decision-making need to be clear;
4. The effectiveness of meetings between partners is absolutely critical to the progress of work. An inconclusive meeting can cause serious delays, risks and costs;
5. Effective collaboration requires central coordination and logistics support. The coordination mechanisms, communication flow inside and outside the project are supported by the PREMETS management structure;
6. Resource control will be achieved by evaluating "Earned Value" through the assessment of intermediate level of completion of deliverables.

This document has been prepared to describe the implementation of the above principles.

1.2 Procedure description

Quality planning is an integral part of management planning. As a pre-requisite to its preparation, the Quality Control Panel (2.2.5) has reviewed all requirements in order to determine the necessary activities that need to be planned.

It has been prepared early in the project in order to demonstrate and provide the Consortium with the assurance that:

- contract requirements and conditions have been reviewed,
- effective quality planning has taken place, and
- quality system is appropriate.

To ensure relevance of the quality plan, the Quality Control Panel should conduct quality reviews, throughout the duration of the contract, and when contractual changes occur. The Quality Control Panel shall ensure that the quality plan is available to all partners concerned and that its requirements are met.

2 MANAGEMENT PLAN

2.1 Management structure and procedures

PreMETS project encompasses 13 partners and 7 interdependent work packages. The overall management structure is illustrated in Figure 1 and it has been designed to achieve the following goals:

1. Reasonable distribution of activities and responsibilities among all 13 partners by also considering their respective competences;
2. Efficient vertical and horizontal information flow, especially between work packages;
3. Robust structures and procedures for responsive and cost-effective project management;
4. Optimal assignment of experienced personnel to the scientific, technical and managerial tasks;
5. Identified potential risks and associated contingency plans.

The Project Coordinator undertakes the detailed project planning and delivery responsibility and interfaces with the European Commission for compliance with all requirements. The Management Committee is the superior governing body of the project management and takes the final decisions on policy, contractual issues and conflicts as requested by the Project Coordinator. On the other hand, the Steering Committee makes executive decisions on strategic issues and has a major impact on the success of the partnership. For the purpose of the management and the successful execution of all tasks, the Work Package Leaders and the Task Leaders fulfil these roles. The requirements of tasks and deliverables are specific but relate to the maturity reached by the project in relation to the Quality Control Panel's expectations for the work under review. The Quality Control Panel is responsible for reviewing the project's results and giving the clearance to proceed to the next step. Regarding the updates of the dissemination plan, the Dissemination Group will identify new opportunities and evaluate outcomes and the quality of relevant activities. Finally, the Advisory Board will support the implementation of the PREMETS project providing feedback at key project milestones.

2.2 Project Management

2.2.1 Project Coordinator (PC)

The Hellenic Institute of Transport of the Centre for Research and Technology Hellas (CERTH) is the project Coordinator (PC) for both administrative and technical aspects. The PC is the liaison between the project and the European Commission (EC) which is represented by the Project Officer (PO). The

PC is responsible for the quality of work that is being held in the project having the utmost administrative, managerial and scientific responsibility for the PreMETS project. The coordinating body is responsible also to formulate and submit all necessary reports to the EC, which monitors the project's progress.

The main responsibilities of the PC are:

- overall management of the project and, in particular, of administrative duties, scientific and quality assurance, budget monitoring, risk and contingency planning and proper documentation of these issues in conjunction with financial needs;
- reporting of project's findings and consolidation of partner contribution into a single final report;
- interfacing with the European Commission for all necessary issues under the umbrella of PreMETS project (contractual issues, project content, amendments, reporting, communication, dissemination and take-up planning);
- representation to the research community.

2.2.2 Management Committee (MC)

The Management Committee (MC) is the superior governing body of PREMETS. It represents every partner in the Consortium and is empowered to review compliance of members with the Consortium Agreement and with the stated goals of the project. It is composed of one delegate per partner organization and shall meet physically at least once a year and virtually as needed. The MC takes final decisions on policy and contractual issues and conflicts as requested by the Coordinator. Each delegate has one vote; decisions are made by consensus whenever possible. Only in cases where consensus is not possible, decisions are made by majority voting. The majority rule is detailed in the Consortium Agreement.

The main responsibilities of the MC consist of:

- reviewing general project progress with regard to its goals;
- deciding on actions in case of major deviations from the plan;
- discussing and making decisions on changes in the Consortium structure;
- deciding on re-allocation of the budget;
- approving planned contract amendments to the Grant Agreement;
- approving changes to Consortium Agreement;
- deciding on collaborations, if large strategic impacts are expected by the Coordinator;
- resolving conflicts that cannot be solved at lower management levels.

2.2.3 Steering Committee (StC)

The Steering Committee consists of the Coordinator (chair) and all WP leaders. In addition, the StC may include additional members, to ensure that all major project perspectives will be covered. The StC composition will be ratified by the MC. The StC will make executive decisions on strategic issues and will have a major impact on the overall outcomes and success of the partnership. Major decisions concerning overall technological direction of the project will be taken here. The StC will make recommendations for amendments of the EC Grant Agreement for GA ratification. Overall, the StC is subject to the decisions made by the MC.

2.2.4 Work package leaders and task leaders (WPL and TL)

The WP leader (WPL) is responsible for the management and execution of all tasks in the affiliated work package and for resolving any critical issues at WP level. The WPL is responsible for submitting the deliverables produced by its WP to the Management Committee in time. The WPL also reports to the Project Coordinator about the status on a regular basis or when asked for. The WPL should monitor the progress of the work package (in terms of timing of submissions or quality control, scientific context and correspondence to the agreed level of quality) and coordinate the tasks at WP level. In case of any identified delays may have impact to WP deliverables or the deliverables' submission of other WPs the WPL has to inform the PC. Task leader (TL) is responsible for the work to be accomplished at task level. Tasks are components of each work package that include a specific and consistent set of activities, being part of the whole WP. The task leader is responsible for the management and execution of associated task and report to the WPL.

Table 1 – Description of WPs

Work Package No	Work Package Name	Leader
WP1	Project management and coordination	CERTH
WP2	Microcredential certification framework	UPRC
WP3	Predictive manufacturing training content development	HELIXCONNECT
WP4	Microcredential certification framework	CERTH
WP5	PreMETS Predictive Manufacturing Platform	ISIM
WP6	Work-based learning pilots	ATC
WP7	Monitoring and evaluation	EITM

2.2.5 Quality Control Panel

The Quality Control Panel (QCP) will be established for the discussion and review of project's findings and results throughout the duration of the project and will serve as external quality control panel of the work that is elaborated within the PreMETS project. QCP is established to guarantee effective

research results, as well as to enhance their accessibility to key stakeholders and to provide a channel for discussion of the implications of adopting specific policies. The QCP will be consisted of 5 representatives that will be decided in the kick-off meeting. To support better implementation, pairing among partners (administrative mentorship) will be done to help less experienced consortium members handle the implementation flow & administration flow of the project: CERTH-YET; ATC-HELIX; UPI-INTEL; EITM-ISIM; WEG-LCC.

The project will have a strict quality control system for all its outputs and QA will be done firstly through internal peer-review by the QCP (coordinated by the quality manager). Secondly, an external advisory board (EQAB) and External Evaluator will perform quality checks at three levels for each output (prototype/concept, interim draft and final draft). The PreMETS project deliverables will be subject to quality review by the QCP. The responsible author(s) for each deliverable will then be assigned to recompile, adjust, clarify, modify etc. of what has been suggested to be reconsidered. A detailed plan for the internal quality review will foresee the use of a template that will serve as the common backbone for quality assurance reviewers.

The main areas that should be under quality review are:

- The technical approach pursued within the deliverable;
- The level or relation to the objectives of the deliverable as described in the relevant description of work to be done;
- Quality of the results produced within the deliverable in accordance to those expected;
- Format, language, presentation and grammar / syntax.

Each deliverable will be accompanied (introduced) by an executive summary explaining in short, the project phase (understanding, toolkit, implementation, evaluation, guidance), the specific problem addressed in this phase and analyzed in the deliverable, the solution developed for this problem, the value-added of the solution (in comparison with what has been achieved until then), and the exploitation potential of outcomes. In order to strengthen and justify the partner contribution to project deliverables, a contribution form will be distributed to involved partners that should reflect the contribution from each partner (what has been done and how many person months were spent for this). Each partner who will provide input to each deliverable should fill in and send this template to WP leader and Project Coordinator. This will enhance visibility of the work done and provide evidence of the resources allocated.

2.2.6 Dissemination group (DG)

The Dissemination Group (DG) consists of the Coordinator, QM, and the leader of the Dissemination WP (WP7). The project Dissemination Leader is EITM. The dissemination group will meet regularly in teleconferences to review and plan the dissemination activities. The role of the DG is to review the updates of the dissemination plan, to identify new dissemination opportunities, and to evaluate the outcomes and the quality of the dissemination activities.

2.2.7 Quality assurance & evaluation

A quality plan will be developed to define specific quality performance indicators in each output of the project based on: (i) process and project management, (ii) partnership; (iii) results. The quality plan will: define all the evaluation tools that will be used; describe clear evaluation criteria; create a shared understanding of the purposes, use, and users of the evaluation results; foster project's transparency to stakeholders and decision makers; facilitate evaluation capacity building among partners and stakeholders and also best evaluation practices.

2.2.8 Evaluation procedure

The evaluation procedure will be based on: Analysis of project outputs and long-term outcomes (including the identification of improvements); Observations of interactions during implementation of all project activities; Surveys of personnel from partner organisations; Evaluation forms from participants in dissemination events and PreMETS blended pilots; Assessment of the skill-gap mitigation of target groups (beginning vs end of the project) via competence grids; External peer review based on an External Quality Assurance Board (EQAB); External evaluation with mid-term and final reports by an appointed External Evaluator (see WP6). A sample of the quality assurance and evaluation indicators can be found below:

Table 2 – Quality/Evaluation indicators during the project implementation timeline

Indicator	Base value	Target value	Measurement unit	Measurement method
PM modules developed and integrated into university curricula (quant)	0	6	Number of modules	Complete learning pack developed
PM modules developed and integrated into VET curricula (quant)	0	6	Number of modules	Complete learning pack developed
Number of train-the-trainers modules (quant)	0	8	Number of modules	Complete learning pack
Number of trained learners on PM (quant)	0	1000	Number of registrations	Record/log keeping
Number of trained trainers in PM (quant)	0	250	# of certifications	Record/log keeping
Number of certified learners via microcredentials (quant)	0	500	# of certifications	Record/log keeping
Number of learners from social groups at risk involved in the project (quant)	0	300	Number of registrations	Record/log keeping
Number of learners involved in blended	0	50	Number of	Record/log keeping

work based learning secondments (quant)			registrations	
Number of companies engaged in the PreMETS platform (quant)	0	20	Number of companies	Record/log keeping
Number of universities and VET centres that will uptake the PreMETS platform (quant)	0	50	Number of institutions	Record/log keeping
Number of modernised university and VET related PM curricula (quant)	0	25	Number of units	Record/log keeping
Learner satisfaction with regards to the PreMETS online platform (quant + qual) - 35% increase from day 1 to end of training	0	> 85% satisfaction with	1-5 scale index	Perceptions survey with regards to learner satisfaction
Make PM workforce more productive (quant)	Index-based	20% increase	Productivity metrics	Checking company reports
Learner digital competence increase (sample of 1000 learners) (quant)	after pre-assessment	20% increase	1-5 point scale for DigComp	Self-assessed DigComp survey (pre and post training)
Learner green competence increase (sample of 1000 learners) (quant)	after pre-assessment	15% increase	1-5 point scale for GreenComp	Self-assessed GreenComp survey (pre and post training)
Learner entrepreneurship competence increase (sample of 1000 learners) (quant)	after pre-assessment	25% increase	1-5 point scale for EntreComp	Self-assessed EntreComp survey (pre and post training)
Trainer competence increase with regards to online education delivery(sample of 250 trainers) (quant)	after pre-assessment	25% increase	1-5 point scale for DigCompEdu	Self-assessed DigCompEdu survey (pre and post training)
Number of dropouts from university/VET (quant)	after pre-assessment	15% decrease	Number of learners	Comparing drop-outs in year 1 and in year 3 learners database
Amount of funding obtained to sustain PreMETS activities (quant)	0	500 000 EUR	EUR	Combined budget from new projects acquired to sustain PreMETS' efforts
# of policy makers interested to use PreMETS platform for promoting regional safety, sustainability and industrial resilience (quant)	0	10	Number of policy makers	Record/log keeping
Number of companies outside of the consortium interested to use PreMETS platform for upskilling their employees (quant)	0	30	Number of companies	Record/log keeping
Make online education more inclusive (quant + qual)	after pre-assessment	45% increase	Subjective/personal reflections	Pre and post assessment (before and after the trainings)
Degree of learners feeling empowered to be in charge of their own learning path (quant + qual)	TBD after pre-assessment	30% increase	Subjective/personal reflections on key indicators	Pre and post assessment (before and after the trainings)
Increase of employability	Statistical average	15-30% increase in 6-12 months	Percentage	Comparing yearly statistics

Overall satisfaction level of the involved project team (quant + qual)	0	>85%	Subjective reflections	Post assessment at the project completion
Social media engagements / reactions (quant)	0	100 000	# of reaction	Social media metrics
Website visitors (quant)	0	5000	# of visitors	Google analytics
Implementation conformance (quant)	0	<10% change	Percentage	Measuring timeline changes

2.2.9 Monitoring and evaluation process

PreMETS' quality processes will be led by HELIXCONNECT, specifically by Dr Adrian Solomon (quality assurance manager – QAM) who has strong expertise in producing high quality Erasmus+ project results. He will chair a quality control committee composed of members from each partner organisation. The Quality Assurance Manager (from HELIXCONNECT), Project Manager (from CERTH), the Steering Group & EQAB will have the task of ensuring monitoring and evaluation of the progress made towards objectives and results envisaged. Quality control and evaluation points: Financial management: formal reporting, every 6 months; informal reporting - every 3 months; Project implementation (timeline) quality check every 1 month during the monthly calls; Deliverable/result/activity sign off timeline, to be submitted to quality control 2 months prior to sign off deadline to be subjected to internal peer review and 1 month before sign-off to external peer review (to the external advisory board). This applies to both formal results as well as to progress results (i.e. pilot methodologies, dissemination materials, etc all broken down per task define in each WP); Staff engagement and involvement levels, to be monitored every 3 months via surveys; Project meeting evaluation: right after their accomplishment using an online questionnaire developed by HELIXCONNECT and focusing on 3 dimensions: before the meeting, during the meeting and after the meeting; Evaluation of dissemination events will be done using evaluation questionnaires (right after each event) developed by HELIXCONNECT focusing on 3 dimensions: organisation, facilitators, personal experience; Evaluation of the platform pilots will be done using evaluation questionnaires (before & after each event) developed by HELIXCONNECT focusing on 3 dimensions: organisation, facilitators, personal experience, interaction & engagement, ease of technology use, competence level (before and after); All the above will be integrated into Interim quality reports - every 6 months; External evaluation by an appointed evaluator (mid-term and final). All of the above quality checks will be built around SWOT analyses items: Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats, both in a quantitative and qualitative assessment in order to enable a true improvement identification.

2.2.10 External quality assurance board (EQAB)

An advisory board of five (5) external, independent experts, representatives of top-rated projects and influencers in the field will be created and established, covering the identified PreMETS themes, so as

to closely monitor and directly provide consultation to the training and capacity-building development activities.

2.2.11 Consortium as a whole

The PreMETS project Consortium includes 13 partners from 8 countries (presented in the table below).

Table 3 – PreMETS Partners

No	Consortium	Short Name	Country	Profile
1	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS	CERTH	EL	Research center
2	YET ASTIKI MI KERDOSKOPIKI ETAIREIA	YET	EL	Training centre
3	UNIVERSITY OF PIRAEUS RESEARCH CENTER	UPRC	EL	Research organisation
4	HELIXCONNECT EUROPE SRL	HELIXCONNECT	RO	Research centre
5	INSTITUTUL NATIONAL DE CERCETARE DEZVOLTARE IN SUDURA SI INCERCARI DE MATERIALE - ISIM TIMISOARA	ISIM	RO	Public certified VET provider
6	NANO INTELIFORM SRL	INTEL	RO	Manufacturing SME
7	EIT MANUFACTURING EAST GMBH	EITM	AT	European level Institute
8	VISOKOSKOLSKA USTANOVA METROPOLITANUNIVERZITET BEOGRADU	MUB	RS	Private university
9	LODZKA IZBA PRZEMYSLOWO-HANDLOWA	ŁIPH (LCC)	PL	Private institution
10	DEEP BLUE SRL	DEEP BLUE (DB)	IT	Research and Consultancy SME
11	ACCELIGENCE LTD	ACC	CY	SME
12	FOUNDATION WEGEMT - A EUROPEAN ASSOCIATION OF UNIVERSITIES IN MARINE TECHNOLOGY AND RELATED SCIENCES	WEGEMT	NL	European Association
13	ATLANTIS ENGINEERING AE	ATC	EL	SME

PreMETS has a very well-defined and professional consortium management and coordination process as shown in the respective section of the application, however, what is more important, PreMETS puts a strong emphasis on team spirit especially since part of the activities will be done online, with the risk of disengagement. To this end, there are several mitigating factors that will ensure a strong team spirit and an excellent cooperation: Firstly, the partners have past collaboration experience: i.e. HELIX and YET collaborated in more than 7 Erasmus+ projects, YET and CERTH collaborated in 3 such projects as well as in regional events that aimed at spurring competence-building, HELIX and UIP staff collaborated in past industrial MSc programme delivery (university level), CERTH, UIP and ATC are constant partners in intensive R&D projects in the field of transport, manufacturing and industrial engineering, CERTH has long lasting collaboration with DB, ACC and WEG while HELIX has been collaborating for 2 years with INTEL, LCC and MUB on different proposals, transnational initiatives and capacity building actions, INTEL and ISIM have been previously involved in regional projects aimed at developing VET education programmes, HELIX and EITM have an intensive collaboration as part of the EIT-HEI initiative and efforts to transform universities. Secondly, the project will promote

a dual team-spirit: both during task implementation by instituting a collegial work environment and actively promoting a helpful attitude (coordinator is in charge and WP leaders will implement such an approach); as well as socially: PreMETS will ensure that team building and social activities are included during the in-person events as well as that informal social interaction (i.e., Whatsapp groups, hybrid social cafes before/after formal meetings) will be enabled in order to facilitate a quicker and more stable team bonding. Thirdly, to devise a proper team building strategy, the partners will agree on a standardised set of methods during the kick off meeting that will be constantly updated based on the needs and on the measured engagement level of the team.

2.2.12 Consortium management and decision-making

PreMETS employs best practices experienced by its project partners (from more than 300 successfully completed past funded projects) and operates on a management structure built upon four distinct control and action levels: Micro-level: Strategy: focusing on task-level activities, innovations & conceptual development (represented through the work packages (WPs)); Meso-level: Strategy: focusing on higher level project strategy and policy (Strategic Committee (SC)); Meso-level: Executive and operative level focusing on activities to be implemented through WPs to realize the defined strategy (overall coordinated through the General Assembly (GA)) Macro-level: Transnational Steering level involving external monitoring of project activities via the EQAB. The proposed coordination levels will be designed, implemented and monitored via a Consortium Agreement (CA) describing the main management bodies and the decision-making process that will be signed between the parties before the start of the project. The project will be led by the General Project Coordinator (GPC), Dr Vassilis Kappatos, who will be responsible for the overall coordination of PreMETS. He will be supported by a strong scientific team. As Project Coordinator, Dr Kappatos will be the interface with the EACEA Officers and will lead both the SC and GA. Together with the scientific team, he will be ultimate responsible for

monitoring the project activities, for maintaining the communication flow within the Consortium and for managing financial and legal issues. He will preside over all project meetings and will be responsible for circulating the meeting agendas and the follow-up documentation. In executing administrative, legal and financial tasks, Dr Kappatos will be supported by a specialized in-house team (Management Support Team) which specializes in EU Project Management and which will ensure high quality management for PreMETS. This team has successfully managed (completed) several EU funded projects from their inception phase until the delivery and closure (covering all kinds of involved operations). The operative structure for the scientific and technical management of the project is based on five Work Packages, each led by a WP Leader (WPL), who will coordinate and monitor the activities taken within that WP. The management/organizational structure covers the following units:

Table 4 – PreMETS Management/Organizational Structure

Strategic Committee (SC)	General Assembly (GA)	WP Leaders (WPLs)	External Quality Advisory Board (EQAB)
<p>Consists of the GPC and the WP leaders and is the key decision making committee of PreMETS. The SC is in charge of monitoring the project implementation including risk management (and dispute settlement with efficient task re-assignment) and periodic reporting. The milestones and deliverables will be the key measurements against the envisioned implementation timeline. The SC will handle the IPR process under the coordination of the GPC.</p>	<p>The GA is responsible for discussing the technical direction of the project and confirming or revising the strategic guidelines set by the SC. The coordinator will govern the GA which is formed of representatives from each project partner. The GA (due to its high-level representation) will also be in charge of any consortium.</p>	<p>WPLs are in charge of coordinating the operations of each WP (including activity management and implementation with the responsible activity leaders) in terms of meeting the objectives, reaching the milestones and delivering appropriate outputs, according to the WP schedule. WPLs will manage each activity and review the deliverables and report to the SC.</p>	<p>The EQAB members (scientists, industrial & policy representatives) are internationally renowned, independent experts working in the areas covered by PreMETS. The EQAB will be managed by the SC and GPC. The EQAB will review technical results of the project and give non-binding advice towards further advancements to be achieved. They will join PreMETS project meetings once per year.</p>

The decision-making mechanism of PreMETS will be based such as: Level 1 - The SC. Decisions regarding exchanges of tasks and/or reallocation of resources within the WPs, as well as the approval of procedures to ensure an effective day-to-day management, will be taken at this first level under the supervision of the GPC and with the agreement of any additional partners that are specifically involved in or from the decision. As an example, the SC decision could concern a major change in the work plan or changes in the allocation of activities and budget among the members of the Consortium, provided they do not significantly change the project objectives and outputs. The SC will also have to settle any internal controversies between project partners. The SC will hold a monthly meeting using digital means and will also meet in each one of the scheduled Project Meetings; Level 2 - The GA (in case the SC cannot reach a decision). The GA will adopt decisions on the basis of a majority vote, each present partner having one vote, if full consensus during the meeting cannot be reached. The GPC will regulate in detail which type of decisions can be taken from the SC with no involvement of the GA, and especially in case of controversies among partners; Level 3 – The EACEA. It intervenes when the decision leads to a contractual change, for example if a new beneficiary asks to enter in the Consortium, or if, for any reason, beneficiary needs to be substituted. In these cases, the GPC will inform the EACEA, based on decisions taken by the GA; then the EACEA will express its position that is legally binding for the Consortium. The EACEA intervenes also if an amendment in the GA is needed. Although e-mail voting could be necessary for very urgent matter, the favoured time to take decisions will be during synchronous meetings (online or offline), either SC or GAs.

2.2.13 Consortium management and decision-making

Some preliminary risks and proposed risk-mitigation measures are included in the table below.

Table 5 – PreMETS Critical risks and risk management strategy

Risk No	Description	Work package No	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
1	QUALITY	All WPs	The project will have a strict quality control system for all its outputs and QA will be done firstly through internal peer-review (coordinated by the quality manager). Secondly, an external advisory board (EQAB) and External Evaluator will perform quality checks at three levels for each output (prototype/concept, interim draft and final draft).
2	LACK OF COMMUNICATION	All WPs	The lead partner will organize an emailing list with all the relevant contacts from each project partner and will maintain constant internal communication. Partners will informally report every month during the monthly online meetings, and formally, every six months for the project management and quality reports.
3	IMPLEMENTATION DELAY	All WPs	Such risks could consist (primarily) of: inability to produce all the results prior to the initiation of the virtual pilots which would therefore hinder the quality of the virtual pilots. This risk will be mitigated (firstly) through the past experience of each project partner in Erasmus+ projects as well as through the high quality of staff profiles involved in the implementation. The milestones & objectives will be monitored every month and corrective actions will be taken in case of delays.
4	FINANCIAL & ADMINISTRATIVE RISKS	WP1	Such as: underspending, overspending, payment delays, reporting delays. These will be mitigated via the creation of a budget spreadsheet in order to calculate and estimate spend. The costs will be reviewed and discussed at the first steering group. We will constantly compare actual spend and deliverables.
5	NOT REACHING THE PARTICIPANT TARGETS	WP5	Each partner already has confirmed cross- departmental staff profiles involved in the project. For the dissemination and piloting events we will heavily advertise the events to large audiences and we will engage the local quadruple helix actors as supporters/co-organizers to receive therefore multilateral endorsements and therefore, attract the audience. Second trials for the events which do not meet the targets to be done.
6	PLATFORM DEPLOYMENT	WP4, WP7	All the outputs of the project are part of the internal goals of each project partners, henceforth, all the outputs will be automatically embedded and used across all organizational levels from the project partners. A clear exploitation plan will be agreed upon within the first months of the project and formalized towards the end of the project.
7	COVID-19 Risks	WP5	PreMETS can sustain 100% online activities and the internal digital skills will be enhanced even more via the digital result development. The majority of the partners are knowledge based institutions and do not have operational impact due to any COVID-19 restrictions.
8	Limited impact of Dissemination	WP7	Translation of scientific knowledge into plain and engaging language to engage the audience. Project dedicated demonstrations, and relevant training events are also planned with the active participation of relevant stakeholders to training events, related projects, conferences, etc). Professional marketing services will be employed.
9	Data sharing reluctance	WP5	The participating companies will devise non-disclosure agreements with the participants by developing formal internship contracts with the trainees.
10	Competitive courses	WP2	We will continuously monitor the state of the art and adapt our work development by re-focusing research efforts and integrating third-party results.

2.2.14 Project Management Arrangements

The project's coordinator will prepare and bootstrap the allocation of resources to the partners, and the Consortium Agreement will be drafted to guide the overall coordination process. The Consortium Agreement document will define important issues about the partners' roles and responsibilities during the project's implementation phase. Examples of such matters are legal obligations, rights and responsibilities, conflict of interests, confidentiality issues, the use of open-access licences, IPR issues, decision-making procedures, voting processes, project oversight and Quality Control, conflict resolution processes, description of Tasks (detailed spreadsheet as per allocated role and responsibilities to include name of each WP and activity to take part in, specific task, expected input and output, comments on format/specificity), timing of activities (detailed spreadsheet with the specific timeframe for delivering each task, indicative start and end date), estimated budget (general overview of project budget, detailed overview of allocated budget as per agreed roles, responsibilities and programme rules, tasks to be carried out, cost to be covered, number of units allocated, budget per unit allocated), project Implementation plan (to include all rules /financial and management/ and requirements to be followed during the project lifetime) and the rest of the legal provisions related to suspension and termination, financial provisions, payment arrangements, recovery, reimbursement, etc. will be outlined. Other important matters will be included in the Consortium Agreement, such as payment and reporting procedures, scope, timeframe, bank accounts; data controller and communication details of partners, applicable law, special provisions, etc. The document will be prepared by the project's coordinator upon the EACEA's communication on the project funding decision and will be signed by all partners at a very early stage of the project, ensuring that each partner is perfectly knowledgeable on what, when and how they will be contributing to project deployment. To support better implementation, pairing among partners (administrative mentorship) will be done to help less experienced consortium members handle the implementation flow & administration flow of the project: CERTH-YET; ATC-HELIX; UPI-INTEL; EITM-ISIM; WEG-LCC.

Deliverables and outputs schedules will be drawn up by the organisation responsible for leading each output, agreed with the PM clearly stating the expectations and contributions of consortium members to each output. This will be incorporated into the project agenda. The PM will ensure that regular communication takes place between all partners using emails, teleconferencing, and cloud computing applications to facilitate discussions and share project documents, ensuring smooth and effective partnership working and exploiting opportunities for cross-institutional collaborations and dissemination activities. All meetings will be virtual (by default) in order to mitigate restrictions and to maximise the time dedicated to the project. Budget will be allocated just in case the opportunity arises for several face to face meetings (less than 50% of the total meetings). The formal semestrial

meetings will take place at key stages such as: Meeting 1 – kick-off (M1, in person in Thessaloniki, Greece, organized by CERTH); Meeting 2 (M6, online, organized by HELIX), Meeting 3 (M12, in person in Nicosia, Cyprus organized by ACC), Meeting 4 (M18, in conjunction with the train the learners/trainers pre-pilot, organized in Timisoara by ISIM), Meeting 5 (M24, in conjunction with pilot 2 in Thessaloniki, Greece by YET), Meeting 6 (M30, online, by MUB) and Meeting 7 (closure and final launching event in Athens by UPRC).

The project management strategy includes monitoring of all milestones and reporting system for delays and difficulties to the project advisory board. To achieve this, three interim progress reports will be produced describing the project's progress towards achieving the set goals, as well as two annual project reports, complemented by monthly Zoom/Webex meetings. Partners will lead on outputs to which best reflect their expertise. The PM & SG will agree with all partners the protocols and financial and monitoring procedures, communication means, delivery strategy, timeframes and will develop and agree the detailed project work plan. The project coordinator is in charge of the financial management of the project, but all partners will help to develop and agree on the financial procedures and distribution of resources required for each activity. The lead partner/coordinator, will also ensure the following: Contractual, legal, ethical, financial and administrative management of the consortium; Data Management Plan for primary data (Surveys, participant data, etc, in compliance with GDPR); Ensuring the Consortium Agreement (CA) is kept updated and managed appropriately; Organising and chairing Project Management and transnational meetings; Collation of cost statements, coordination of payments and distribution to relevant consortium members; Facilitating audits and overall communication and interaction with EACEA; Coordinate project activities among activity leaders. Ultimately, task management-wise, PreMETS will adopt the following structure: Each Work Package (WP) is implemented by a core group of partners, led by the respective WP leader. Each Task within every WP is also led by the Task owner. These are the basic coordination characteristics for managing the project's implementation ensuring that every activity is in-line with the initial proposal, the grant agreement with EACEA and the Consortium Agreement. In M1, each partner will nominate one representative member to take important operational decisions on behalf of its organisation. Additionally, all consortium members will have to provide nominations for core groups (WP and Task managers), as per allocated roles within each work package.

2.2.15 Transnational dimension & EU impact/interest & cross-border cooperation potential

Transnational cooperation is required and beneficial because: The skill-gap in the involved countries is similar and therefore, this transnational EU cooperation will solve a common need; Moreover, in the involved countries, more than 47% of the digital learners (higher education and VET) face

inclusion and engagement challenges; Southern (Italy, Greece, Cyprus) and Eastern Europe (Romania, Serbia) are among the countries in the EU with the highest rate of unqualified trainers (poor quality qualification systems for trainers in various educational sector) and therefore, by working together this challenge can be mitigated³⁵; Similarly, the East – West/Centre (Netherlands, Austria) divide within the EU in terms of up-skilling, inclusion and access to quality educational resources can also be mitigated via this transnational cooperation; By working at a transnational level, specific cultural(national) backgrounds, behaviours and nuances can be blended towards ensuring a more homogenous and applied mix of results that can then be replicated to the countries nearing this cooperation block involved in PreMETS; As the project results will be made available in full digital content (accessible from anywhere), blending a transnational approach can only lead to a successful pan-EU multiplication of the results and of the harmonisation of EU qualifications and efforts; The project also aims to establish a "PreMETS alumni network" at an international dimension and therefore international cooperation can maximise this effort;The topic of PM is a EU-level challenge and often industries that work transnational (EU and beyond) partnerships and supply chains propagate their processes across all locations, therefore if key nodes of industrial actors become trained on PM, they will propagate/impose the trainings to their business partners to ensure operational coordination, reaching the wider EU-span (and beyond); The PreMETS platform, particularly its virtual factory setting (for real life application of knowledge in a blended manner) will include industrial and educational providers from across the EU.

2.3 Gantt chart

The schedule listing the project's milestones, activities, and tasks with estimations in terms of duration is shown in the Gantt chart below.

ACTIVITY	YEAR 1				YEAR 2				YEAR 3			
	Q 1	Q 2	Q 3	Q 4	Q 1	Q 2	Q 3	Q 4	Q 1	Q 2	Q 3	Q 4
WP1 - Task 1.1 Consortium management	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
WP1 - Task 1.2 IPR, legal and ethical task management	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
WP1 – Task 1.3 Reporting to the EACEA	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
WP1 – Task 1.4 Managing the EQAB	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
WP2 – Task 2.1 Foresight exercises	■											
WP2 – Task 2.2 PM training toolkit development		■	■									
WP2 – Task 2.3 PM training toolkit peer review			■									

WP2 – Task 2.4 VET Certification				■								
WP2 – Task 2.5 Higher Education Certification				■								
WP2 – Task 2.6 Train-the-trainers toolkit development		■	■									
WP2 – Task 2.7 Train-the-trainers toolkit peer review			■									
WP3 – Task 3.1 Microcredential certification framework				■								
WP3 – Task 3.2 Microcredential assessment development					■							
WP3 – Task 3.3 Microcredential certificate development					■							
WP3 – Task 3.4 Operational guidelines					■							
WP4 – Task 4.1 Requirements specification confirmation					■							
WP4 – Task 4.2 Platform development					■	■						

WP4 – Task 4.3 Platform beta testing					■							
WP4 – Task 4.4 Platform documentation and deployment						■						
WP5 – Task 5.1 Work based learning pilot methodology					■							
WP5 – Task 5.2 Trainers’ pre-pilot						■						
WP5 – Task 5.3 Learners’ pre-pilot						■						
WP5 – Task 5.4 WBL Pilot 1							■					
WP5 – Task 5.5 WBL Pilot 2								■				
WP5 – Task 5.6 Pilot reporting and evaluation									■			
WP5 – Task 5.7 Mass virtual pilot										■		
WP6 – Task 6.1 Quality assurance plan	■											
WP6 – Task 6.2 VET & HEI hybrid learning QA plan	■											
WP6 – Task 6.3 Applied quality assurance guide	■											
WP6 – Task 6.4 Periodic quality reviews		■		■		■		■		■		■
WP6 – Task 6.5 External evaluator selection	■											
WP6 – Task 6.6 External evaluation strategy		■										
WP6 – Task 6.7 External							■					■

evaluation deployment													
WP7 – Task 7.1 Communication and dissemination plan													
WP7 – Task 7.2 Communication infrastructures													
WP7 – Task 7.3 Communication & dissemination activities													
WP7 – Task 7.4 Impact measurement plan													
WP7 – Task 7.5 10-year sustainability plan													

The Coordinator monitors and coordinates the work plan.

After 18 months, the PreMETS project will provide the reporting on activities and resources, and any deviations from the original work plan will be explained and justified in the periodic reports. The Project Coordinator will revise the Gantt chart accordingly, updating it with actual effort reported, actual month of submission of the deliverables and main project meetings that took place.

In particular, the Project Officer will monitor the effort allocation to the tasks/deliverables provided by partners in order to check the status of the use of resources.

The WP leader is responsible for the schedule within his/her WP and he/she must communicate with the Coordinator in case any problems or delays that may rise during the project timeline.

2.4 Deliverable Process

The list of PreMETS deliverables is reported in the following table.

Table 7 – List of Deliverables

Deliverable No	Deliverable Name	Work Package No	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month number)	Description (including format and language)
D1.1	Project management plan	1	CERTH	[R – Document, report]	[PU – Public]	M1	A report (50 pages, English) containing all internal management and coordination procedures.
D1.2	Data management plan	1	CERTH	[DMP – Data Management Plan]	[PU – Public]	M1	A document (10 pages, English) explaining the PreMETS data management strategy.
D2.1	Future PM employee profile	2	HELIX	[R – Document, report]	[PU – Public]	M3	A report (10 pages) describing the future employee profile in the field of PM. The entire content will be made available in EN, RO, GR,

							IT, DE, NE, SRB.
D2.2	PM training toolkit	2	UPI	[R — Document, report] [OTHER]	[PU — Public]	M12	A compendium of documents covering content for 6 training modules: 300 slides with voice/video overlay, 5 storyboards, 1 booklet (300 pages), collection of 20 demonstrative videos, 1 interactive learner-persona based simulator as assessment tool (180 multiple-choice questions) and 1 webquest per module related to work-based learning practices. Languages: EN, RO, GR, IT, DE, NE, SRB.
D2.3	PM training toolkit VET certification strategy	2	ISIM	[R — Document, report]	[PU — Public]	M12	This is a 15-page report consisting of the VET certification guidelines for the content from D2.2. It will contain number of contact hours, institutional integration guidelines, assessment, and work-based learning integrations. Full integration with ECVET/EQUAVET. The entire content will be made available in EN, RO, GR, IT, DE, NE, SRB.
D2.4	PM training toolkit higher education certification strategy	2	UPI	[R — Document, report]	[PU — Public]	M12	This is a 15-page report consisting of the higher education certification guidelines for the content from D2.2. It will contain number of contact hours, institutional integration guidelines, assessment, and work-based learning integrations. Full ECTS/EQUIS integration. The entire content will be made available in EN, RO, GR, IT, DE, NE, SRB.
D2.5	Train-the-trainers toolkit	2	MUB	[R — Document, report]	[PU — Public]	M12	A compendium of documents covering content for 8 training modules: slides with voice/video overlay (160 in total), 1

							storyboard, 1 booklets (160 pages in total), collection of 10 demonstrative videos, 1 interactive learner-persona based simulator as assessment tool (160 questions) and 1 webquest per module as an applied online education delivery task. Languages: EN, RO, GR, IT, DE, NE, SRB.
D3.1	PreMETS certification framework	3	UPI	[R — Document, report]	[PU — Public]	M12	An integrated report covering the results of Tasks 3.1 and 3.2. Size: 50 Pages report available in EN, RO, GR, IT, DE, NE, SRB.
D3.2	PreMETS digital certificate/cr edential	3	CERTH	[DEC — software]	[PU — Public]	M15	A digital credential issued via Europass Digital Digital Credentials App as well as a standalone XML certificate file.
D4.1	PreMETS Platform	4	CERTH	[DEC — Websites, patent filings, videos, etc]	[PU — Public]	M21	The PreMETS platform successfully launched and tested. The platform will be available in EN, RO, GR, IT, DE, NE, SRB.
D4.2	PreMETS platform operational and integration guidelines	4	CERTH	[R — Document, report]	[PU — Public]	M21	A report containing guidelines for the PreMETS platform to ensure that any interested party can replicate it: 30 Pages report available in EN, RO, GR, IT, DE, NE, SRB.
D5.1	WBL Pilot 1	5	INTEL	[DEM — Demonstrator, pilot, prototype]	[PU — Public]	M24	Successful implementation of the 3-month pilot (see Task 5.4)
D5.2	WBL Pilot 2	5	UPI	[DEM — Demonstrator, pilot, prototype]	[PU — Public]	M27	Successful implementation of the 3-month pilot (see Task 5.5)
D5.3	Mass virtual pilot	5	EITM	[DEM — Demonstrator, pilot, prototype]	[PU — Public]	M33	Successful implementation of the virtual pilot (see Task 5.7)
D5.4	Pilot reporting and evaluation	5	ISIM	[R — Document, report]	[PU — Public]	M33	Report covering lessons learned (Task 5.6) and suggestions/implications (50 pages, EN, RO, GR, IT, DE, NE, SRB.)
D6.1	Macro quality	6	HELIX	[R — Document,	[PU — Public]	M3	An integrated report (80 pages) containing:

	assurance plan			report]			Quality assurance plan (Task 6.1), VET/HEI quality assurance guidelines (Task 6.2) and the applied quality assurance guide (Task 6.3). Will be issued in EN, RO, GR, IT, DE, NE, SRB.
D6.2	Internal quality assurance report	6	HELIX	[R — Document, report]	[PU — Public]	M18 and M36	An integrated quality assurance report issued as a result of period quality controls of all the declared indicators. One interim report (50 pages) and one updated final report (50 pages) will be issued in English.
D6.3	External evaluation strategy	6	CERTH	[R — Document, report]	[PU — Public]	M6	An initial report explaining the external evaluation (at least 50 pages in English).
D6.4	External evaluation report	6	CERTH	[R — Document, report]	[PU — Public]	M18 and M36	One interim report (50 pages) and one updated final report (50 pages) will be issued in English as part of the external evaluation task.
D7.1	Communication and dissemination plan	7	EITM	[R — Document, report]	[PU — Public]	M3	A report (50 pages, English).
D7.2	Project visual identity pack	7	YET	[DEC — Websites, patent filings, videos, etc]	[PU — Public]	M3	Project website (translation into EN, RO, GR, IT, DE, NE, SRB.). Project logo and visual themes/guidelines Social media accounts setup
D7.3	Mailing list	7	YET	[DATA — data sets, microdata, etc]	[Classified C-UE/EU-C]	M36	A full (decentralized) mailing list with qualified contacts from each project partner (GDPR-compliant) of at least 10 000 contacts.
D7.4	Newsletters & fliers	7	YET	[DEC — Websites, patent filings, videos, etc]	[PU — Public]	M6, M12, M18, M24, M30, M36	6 newsletters in English (digital) with limited printed version (600) distributed to at least 10 000 contacts: in EN, RO, GR, IT, DE, NE, SRB..
D7.5	Storytelling videos	7	YET	[DEC — Websites, patent filings,	[PU — Public]	M36	6 videos developed and disseminated to 20 000 contacts. Videos will be in English with subtitles

				videos, etc]			in RO, GR, IT, DE, NE, SRB.
D7.6	Policy briefings	7	HELIX	[R — Document, report]	[PU — Public]	M36	2 policy briefings (15 pages each) will be developed and made available in EN, RO, GR, IT, DE, NE, SRB.
D7.7	Open day events	7	HELIX	[DEM — Demonstrator, pilot, prototype]	[PU — Public]	M36	8 open day dissemination events will be hosted (each) partner.
D7.8	Media outlet events	7	YET	[DEC — Websites, patent filings, videos]	[PU — Public]	M36	At least 6 appearances in TV/radio/conventional media will be produced.
D7.9	Impact measurement plan with a preliminary impact assessment	7	DB	[R — Document, report]	[PU — Public]	M3 & M36	Impact assessment report (40 pages in EN, RO, GR, IT, DE, NE, SRB.).
D7.10	PreMETS 10-year sustainability & commercialization plan	7	HELIX	[R — Document, report]	[PU — Public]	M36	One report(20 pages) will be developed and made available in EN, RO, GR, IT, DE, NE, SRB.

2.4.1 The Short-Deliverable Policy

The right size for a given deliverable depends largely on the topic, the purpose, etc., but very long deliverables create several problems:

- It takes longer to write and revise them;
- They are not easily readable and prone to lose their focus.

Therefore, the deliverables should be clear about the objective, and then be very concise about the content to include in the documents. The focus must be clear and specific. It must also avoid repeating content from other documents (always use references for that).

It is of utmost importance to have a clear Executive Summary, an Introduction containing the objectives and the structure of the document, as well as a Conclusions section.

All the project official documents will be produced according to the templates and guidelines.

The official editing tool for deliverables will be: Microsoft Word 2010 or newer. Other editing suite tools can be used under the following conditions:

- Deliverable editor must agree with contributors in advance;
- Deliverable editor must provide the template for the new format that must match with the official template provided by the EC;
- If a contributor does not use the selected editing tool/format, the deliverable editor is responsible for integrating these contributions in the official editing format/tool.

2.5 H2020 Participant Portal

It is the official EC Portal for the submission of deliverables, technical and financial reporting, ethical requirements and amendments, specifically:

- Submission of project deliverables;
- Periodic Technical & Financial Reporting;
- Final Technical & Financial Reporting;
- Risk & Issues Management;
- Requests for Amendments;
- Implementation of Ethics Requirements;
- Submission of Final Project Results Report.

2.6 Project Meetings

Interactive management meetings and technical meetings play an important role in the project.

PreMETS meetings will include the following.

Table 8 – Events meetings and mobility

Event No	Participant	Description					Attendees Total
		Name	Type	Area	Location	Duration (days)	
E1.1	All	Transnational meeting 1	Project meeting	Project coordination	Thessaloniki, Greece	1.5	26
E1.2	All	Transnational meeting 2	Project meeting	Project coordination	Online	1.5	26
E1.3	All	Transnational meeting 3	Project meeting	Project coordination	Nicosia, Cyprus	1.5	26
E1.4	All	Transnational meeting 1	Project meeting	Project coordination	Timisoara, Romania	1.5	26
E1.5	All	Transnational meeting 1	Project meeting	Project coordination	Online	1.5	26
E1.6	All	Transnational meeting 1	Project meeting	Project coordination	Athens, Greece	1.5	26
E5.1	All	Trainers' pre-pilot	Mobility	Train of trainers	Timisoara, Romania	5	26
E5.2	All	Learners' pre-pilot	Mobility	Work based learning	Thessaloniki, Greece	5	26
E5.3	All	WBL Pilot 1	Internship/event	Predictive manufacturing	Timisoara, Romania	90	25
E5.4	All	WBL Pilot 2	Internship/event	Predictive manufacturing	Thessaloniki, Greece	90	25

				ng			
E7.1	CERTH	Open day 1	Dissemination event	Project output promotion	Thessaloniki, Greece	1	50
E7.2	ISIM	Open day 2	Dissemination event	Project output promotion	Timisoara, Romania	1	50
E7.3	EITM	Open day 3	Dissemination event	Project output promotion	Vienna, Austria	1	50
E7.4	MUB	Open day 4	Dissemination event	Project output promotion	Belgrade, Serbia	1	50
E7.5	LCC	Open day 5	Dissemination event	Project output promotion	Lodz, Poland	1	50
E7.6	DB	Open day 6	Dissemination event	Project output promotion	Rome, Italy	1	50
E7.7	ACC	Open day 7	Dissemination event	Project output promotion	Nicosia, Cyprus	1	50
E7.8	WEG	Open day 8	Dissemination event	Project output promotion	Amsterdam, NE	1	50

2.6.1 Organisation of the meetings

In the paragraphs below, best practices for the organisation of the PreMETS meetings are described.

Types of meetings

There are three types of meetings: (i) face-to-face, (ii) video conference, and (iii) conference call.

The Consortium has planned to physically meet face-to-face at least once a year, where progress periodic meetings will be co-located over a period of 1.5-2 days, at the premises of the project partners (chosen randomly giving equal opportunity to each partner to host meetings). If possible, project meetings can be organized in conjunction with key events that PreMETS partners plan or may have an interest to participate.

The Consortium partners are located in different countries. For the face-to-face meetings it is important to consider:

- If another face-to-face meeting is scheduled at the same time. Verify if it's possible to jointly conduct the two meetings in order to optimize the cost;
- Evaluate the time and, if it's possible, avoid critical timing (e.g., holidays, international events, etc.);
- Evaluate how easy it is to reach the place and city of choice;

- Consider the previous location of the face-to-face meeting giving equal opportunity to each partner to host meetings.

Conference call meetings are foreseen to facilitate partners' collaboration and the organisation of additional meetings. These meetings enjoy the same rules as the other standard meetings and will be used for progress meetings and WP meetings, whenever it is necessary.

Responsibilities of partners

The hosting partner should give information related to arrival and departure times and, where appropriate, recommendations for hotels. The hosting partner is responsible for the coffee breaks, lunches and dinners' organisation taking into account special meals, if needed.

A call bridge should be created to facilitate the participation of people who cannot join (BE OPEN members or EC representative).

Agendas and minutes will be prepared and shared by the chairperson of the meeting and shall be made available to all Consortium members on the Gdrive repository of the PreMETS project.

Each Partner:

- Should be present or represented at any meeting;
- May appoint a substitute or a proxy to attend and vote at any meeting; and
- Shall participate in a cooperative manner in the meetings.

Each participant to a meeting should contribute to the meeting preparation by providing in advance to the meeting:

- Contributions to the agenda;
- Preparation of presentations;
- Working documents: normally the main subjects discussed during a meeting will be documented by discussion papers or presentations. As far as possible, these means should be distributed in advance and not during the meeting itself, since otherwise the participants will be unable to be prepared for the meeting;
- Feedback on the minutes in case of disagreement;
- Execution of actions and respect of decisions.

The Coordinator will have the special responsibility of contributing to the definition of meeting objectives, and the preparation of decisions, agenda and minutes.

The Coordinator for plenary meetings or the WP leader for the WP meetings will be the chairperson, unless decided otherwise.

Agenda of the meetings

Each meeting must have an agenda. The draft agenda should be distributed in advance (10 days), to inform participants about the topics to be discussed and to give them the opportunity to suggest changes to the agenda which must then be re-circulated.

Comments and integration can be done before sharing the final agenda (5 days before the meeting).

The agenda lists the subjects which are planned to be discussed. It is an instrument to assist the facilitator in monitoring the meeting. Secretarial work is also minimised by a well-structured agenda.

Each agenda contains some standard subjects with the following structure:

- type of meeting
- list of participants
- <place>
- <date>
- <time> Opening and welcome.
- <time> Objectives of the meeting and agreement about the agenda.
- <time> Remarks on previous minutes (only if applicable).
- <time> Action points (only if applicable).
- <time> Meeting specific subjects.
- Explanation of subject (issues to decide upon, actions to decide, etc.)
- ...
- <time> Sum up and closing:
 - Date and place of next meeting(s) (only if applicable)
 - Define list of open issues.
 - Summarise decisions and actions list.

<place> is the location of the meeting, <date> is the day for which the agenda is valid; multiple-day meetings have an agenda for each day. <time> defines the planned time to start discussion on a topic.

If breaks, lunch and dinner are planned, these events should be included in the agenda.

During a meeting the agenda can be modified by adding items if it's necessary.

Minutes

Particular attention must be given to the follow-ups of the meeting; it is recommended to send the minutes quickly, check commitment on decisions and actions with absent Partners, ensure that decisions are respected and actions executed.

The Coordinator for general meetings or the WP leader in charge of the agenda is responsible for the minutes drafting. S/he can appoint a person to produce written minutes, which shall be the formal record of what was discussed during the meeting. The minutes shall be sent to all project members (preferably within 10 calendar days of the meeting). The minutes shall be considered as accepted if no one sends an objection (within 7 calendar days from receiving them).

The minutes will therefore constitute a sort of “pocket handbook” with all the data that each of the participants will always have to keep an eye on.

The minutes will reflect major issues that have been discussed. All minutes of periodic meetings will have the same structure. Minutes should contain the following information:

- meeting date;
- location;
- author;
- participants;
- objective of the meeting (brief);
- actual agenda;
- list of documents distributed during the meeting with reference to the author (if applicable);
- and for each point addressed as part of the agenda:
 - summary of discussion (if relevant);
 - decision;
 - open issues;
 - action;
 - supporting information (if relevant).
- summary of the action list;
- place and date of the next meeting (if applicable).

Minutes of meetings involving the EC shall also be distributed via email for review by the EC officer. Action updates should be regularly (monthly) be sent to the EC. For all meetings involving the EC, the EC shall be asked to review the minutes before their approval.

3 QUALITY PLAN PROCEDURE AND EVALUATION

3.1 Review Process

Quality plan is an integral part of Project management. As a pre-requisite to its preparation, the Quality Control Panel has reviewed all requirements in order to determine the necessary activities that need to be planned. It has been prepared early in the project in order to demonstrate and provide the Consortium with the assurance that:

- the contract requirements and conditions have been reviewed,
- effective quality control has taken place, and
- the quality system is appropriate.

To ensure relevance of the quality plan, the Quality Control Panel should conduct quality reviews, throughout the duration of the contract, and when contractual changes occur. Quality Control Panel shall ensure that the quality plan is available to all partners concerned and that its requirements are met.

In order to ensure a clear structure of the quality assurance procedure, the following steps have to be taken into account:

1. A first check of the consistency in style and content is to be done internally in each Work Package Deliverable. This task is carried out by the Work Package leader.
2. Three (3) weeks before the due date of the deliverable, the task leader for the deliverable informs the reviewers nominated about the status of the deliverable.
3. Two (2) weeks before due date the deliverable is sent by the task leader to the nominated reviewer(s) for quality control.
4. The reviewers have 1 week to read and comment on the deliverable.
5. The deliverable authors revise their reports according to the comments received by the reviewers.
6. Three days before due date, the deliverable authors send the updated deliverable to the project Coordinator. The Coordinator performs a final consistency check to ensure proper formatting and consistency with other project deliverables.
7. The project Coordinator forwards the deliverable to the project officer and publishes the deliverable on the Project Platform.

3.2 Evaluation

The evaluation of the deliverables should be based on the following criteria:

1. General comments, which include:
 - Deliverable contents thoroughness
 - Correspondence to project and programme objectives
2. Specific comments, which include:
 - Relevance
 - Response to user needs
 - Soundness of the methodological framework
 - Quality of achievements
 - Quality of presentation of achievements
 - Check of layout, format, spelling, etc.

The evaluation and rating will give a statement whether the deliverable is accepted or not or if modifications are necessary. The quality of the deliverable will be rated as follows:

- Accepted as it is
- Revise with proposed modifications/comments to be addressed
- Rejected based on substantiated comments

4 DOCUMENTATION CONTROL

4.1 Document coding

There will be a unique project document coding system, as indicated in Table below.

Table 9 – Project document coding system

Document Code	Document Type
D	Deliverable
WP	Work Package
PR	Work Packages Plans and Progress Reports
M	Minutes, Action Lists, Decision Lists
C	Correspondence between Partners
L	Legal documents
COM	Commercial documents
GI	Documents of general interest
PU	Public documents
OTH	Other subjects

All official consortium documents in the above table, except from the Deliverables, are cumulatively characterised hereafter as Project Internal Reports (IR).

4.2 Document referencing and Templates

There is a unique document referencing scheme. This is not applicable however for informal data and views exchange between partners. It is only valid for official consortium documents, falling in one of the aforementioned categories.

The project's internal documents template and referencing scheme is being included in Annex B. For official deliverables, a different template and referencing scheme will be used, as presented in Annex A.

4.2.1 Documents standards and layouts

The naming convention for deliverables is the following:

Dx.y_shortname_V00.00.00.status

where:

- Dx.y is the deliverable number, as reported in the cover page of the document, where x is the workpackage number; and y is a number for each deliverable. The resulting identifier must be one of that listed in List of Deliverables of the DoA.
- shortname is a brief name, decided by the document's author(s), that can be easily related to the document content (it can be the title of the deliverable as in the DoA);
- vn.mm.pp is the document version.
 - Working drafts = last two digits: 00-99 = 00.00.xx.
 - (First) draft for submission/review: 00.01.00
 - Subsequent working drafts to use last digits couple again, e.g. 00.01.01
 - Accepted (first) version (EC): 01.00.00
 - The version number has to be also visible on the front page and in the headline of each page.
- status is the status of the document, that can be a) working b) draft or c) final.

Official project deliverables should have a first page template as presented in Annex A. They should also use the structure and page layout (headers / footers) suggested in this Annex. Furthermore, the mainly technical deliverables should abide by the following rules:

- Have a list of abbreviations used within the deliverable.
- Have a Table of Contents.
- Have a List of Figures.
- Have a List of Tables.
- Start with an one-page Executive Summary.
- Include a References (or Bibliography) section after the Conclusions section.
- Include all detailed technical and other information in Annexes.

The authors of a document and the internal approval process will be included in each document.

The EU emblem has to be displayed in all documents and the following disclaimers have to be included:

- **Funding:** *“This Deliverable is part of a project that has received funding from the European Commission under grant agreement No 101108469 under Erasmus+ Programme (ERASMUS) programme”.*

4.3 Data communication protocols

All documents and computer data files sent either by Internet or E-Mail are to be VIRUS checked before issue and to be screened on receipt. If a VIRUS is found, then action is to be taken to purge both the system infected and to notify the sender to prevent a re-occurrence.

If acknowledgement is requested, an explicit request will be included by the sender at the end of the message (E-mail, fax, etc.), stating "Please Acknowledge". Then, the recipient is required to send a message acknowledgement within the next two (2) working days.

4.4 Participation in events and publications

Apart from the official project events, the following are considered dissemination events:

- Publications in relevant Magazines;
- Presentations in Conferences;
- Participation in relevant projects meetings;
- Participation in non-project workshops, forums and/or events.

The participation of any project participant in such an event should be approved beforehand by the Steering Committee, with a written approval sent by the Coordinator (CERTH/HIT).

For any conference presentation or journal publication, the following procedure will be followed:

- Oral agreement of all participants being present at the meeting, or written agreement of the Project Manager. In the latter case, it is the PM's responsibility to request approval from all interested / involved participants. The written answer should be sent from the requesting participant within 5 working days from receipt from the PM. Otherwise, it is supposed to be positive.
- The draft paper is then circulated to all project participants, at least 15 days before submission. All participants may object to the publication of confidential data or to non-inclusion of their name, if their work is also included, within 5 days from receipt of the draft paper. Comments are to be sent to the publishing partner with copies to the Project Manager. Then the CERTH/HIT should restructure the draft paper accordingly.
- After paper acceptance, a copy of the final paper will be sent to the Project Coordinator who will forward the paper abstract and publication information to the Project Officer.

In case of too short deadlines, the actions prior to abstract or paper submission might be realized quicker, after consultation with the Coordinator.

The above rules will be strictly applied and checked by the PM in order to:

- avoid repetition of publication of the same work;
- avoid publication of restrictive and/or commercial in confidence data;
- avoid misunderstandings between participants and publication of one's work without proper referencing;
- secure optimum use of dissemination resources of the project;
- guarantee proper archiving of all dissemination material.

5 INTERNAL COMMUNICATION STRATEGIES

The main Documents that will be circulated between partners are the following:

- Quarterly reports;
- Technical deliverables;
- Internal Reports.

Regarding electronic communication, a series of mailing lists will be compiled to enhance the communication between BE OPEN partners. The mailing lists that will be developed are the following:

- One mailing list for all BE OPEN Partners, which will contain two (or more) e-mail addresses per partner. This mailing list should be used, in case an e-mail is addressed to the whole network.
- One mailing list for Work Package leaders. This mailing list contains from one to four contacts from each partner.

The mailing lists will be distributed as text files to all PreMETS Partners and will also be uploaded in Gdrive, an Internal partners' area that constitutes a documents repository and project management tool. Through Gdrive the participants will be able to exchange documents, download the presentations and minutes of the meetings and in general communicate with one another.

6 Project reporting and monitoring

The action is divided into the following Reporting Periods [1]:

- RP1: from month 1 to month 18;
- RP2: from month 19 to month 36;

The Coordinator must submit a periodic report within 60 days following the end of each reporting period.

Each WP leader should submit a WP Report to the Project Coordinator, who assembles the parts and elaborates the Progress Report.

The Coordinator must submit to the EC the technical and financial reports, including when needed the requests for payment and must be drawn up using forms and templates provided by the EC.

6.1 Periodic Technical/Financial Reporting

A Periodic Technical and Financial Progress Report shall be submitted via the H2020 Participant Portal every six months within 60 working days following the end of the Reporting Period.

The content of the Technical and Financial Progress Reports is detailed in the H2020 User Manual. An extract is provided below; however, the latest version of the H2020 User Manual remains the reference.

6.1.1 Periodic Technical Report

A Technical Progress Report shall provide a qualitative summary of the work performed according to H2020 guidelines. It consists of **Part A** and **Part B**:

Part A contains:

1. the cover page;
2. a publishable summary, including:
 - An executive statement on the progress made and key issues;
 - Achievements made in the last reporting period, i.e. milestones, meetings, and tasks key data;
 - Main targets and events over the next reporting period.
3. Tables covering issues related to the project implementation (e.g., Work Packages, Deliverables, Milestones, etc.) which includes:

- Deliverables (indicating the % completion of deliverables);
 - Milestones;
 - Ethical Issues (if applicable);
 - Critical implementation risks and mitigation measures;
 - Dissemination & exploitation of results;
 - Impact on SMEs (if applicable);
 - Open Research Data (if applicable);
 - Gender.
4. The answers to the questionnaire covering issues related to the project implementation and the economic and social impact, notably in the context of the Horizon 2020 key performance indicators and the Horizon 2020 monitoring requirements.

Part A is generated via the Participant Portal based on the information entered by the participants through the periodic report and continuous reporting modules. The participants can update the information in the continuous reporting module at any time during the project lifetime.

Part B of the periodic technical report provides the narrative part that includes explanations of the work carried out by the beneficiaries during the reporting period. It will include:

1. Explanations of the work carried out by all beneficiaries and linked third parties during the reporting period;
2. An overview of the progress towards the project objectives, justifying the differences between work expected under Annex I and work actually performed, if any;
3. An update on Risks and Issues.

Part B needs to be uploaded as a PDF document. It must be consistent with the template of Part B Periodic Technical report.

6.1.2 Periodic Financial Report

A Financial Progress Report shall be submitted every six months via the H2020 Participant jointly with the Technical Progress Report.

The periodic financial report consists of:

1. Individual financial statements (Annex 4 to the GA) for each beneficiary;

2. Explanation of the use of resources and the information on subcontracting and in-kind contributions provided by third parties from each beneficiary for the reporting period concerned;
3. A periodic summary financial statement including the request for interim payment.

6.1.3 Final Periodic Technical/Financial Report

The Final Report covers the whole project and is composed of a Final Technical and a Final Financial part. It is delivered within 60 days from the completion of the Action.

In case not all deliverables have been submitted in time before the completion of the Action, the Project may ask for an extension, as an exception, using the Amendment procedure.

6.1.4 Final Periodic Technical Report

The Final Periodic Technical Report is a publishable summary of the entire project. It provides:

1. An overview of the project scope and objectives;
2. The achieved results and main conclusions achieved at the end of the project based on the criteria defined by EC supporting the claimed project readiness to transfer its results to the next R&I phase;
3. The performed communication and dissemination actions;
4. The Exploitation and follow-up activities proposed for the next stage of the R&I lifecycle;
5. The socio-economic impact of the project;
6. An up-to-date link to the project website;
7. Project logos, diagrams, photographs and videos illustrating its work (if available).

The final summary must be written in a style understandable for a non-specialist audience. The Coordinator must ensure that none of the material submitted for publication includes confidential or 'EU classified' information.

6.1.5 Final Periodic Financial Report

The Final Periodic Financial Report includes:

1. The final summary financial statement that is automatically created by the system (consolidating the data from all individual financial statements for all beneficiaries and linked third parties, for all reporting periods) and that constitutes the request for payment of the balance;

2. In some cases (and for some beneficiaries/linked third parties) it must be accompanied by a certificate on the financial statements – CFS (one certificate per beneficiary/linked third party).

7 RISKS AND PREVENTIVE ACTIONS

7.1 Risk and conflict management

Every effort will be made to identify potential risks and conflicts as early as possible. The impact of such risks and conflicts on project objectives will be assessed by the project manager and the work package leaders. The impacts will be actively addressed through an early assessment and elimination of risk through the detection of proper actions and management of any dysfunctional conflicts. In cases of dysfunctional conflict, the Consortium will follow a mediation approach to identify possible alternatives and mutually select the one that is in the interest of the project objectives.

7.2 Corrective and preventive actions

Apart from the particular procedures adopted to assess the quality of the Project Deliverables, this section deals with issues related to the general performance of the Partners and the quality of their work-related outcome.

- The Coordinator is responsible for implementing and recording changes in procedures, resulting from corrective actions. Established procedures established are to ensure:
- Effective handling of all complaints,
- Reports of non-conformities,
- Investigation of the cause of non-conformities in relation to the quality system,
- Recording the results of the investigation,
- Determining the corrective / preventing action needed to eliminate the cause of the non-conformity,
- Application of controls to ensure that corrective action is taken and is effective,
- Initiation of preventative action and application of controls to ensure that it is effective,
- Ensuring that relevant information on actions taken is submitted for review.

The Coordinator is responsible for resolving matters of complaint under this procedure, in agreement with the Steering Committee. All complaints have to be investigated and corrective action agreed. The QM informs all involved for the complaints and the actions being taken. The complaints are recorded in a Complaint Register and are being controlled. Corrective actions are recorded and all involved are informed of the action taken.

8 REFERENCES

[1] PreMETS Grant Agreement

ANNEX A: DELIVERABLES' TEMPLATE

Project: 101108469 — PreMETS — ERASMUS-EDU-2022-PI-ALL-INNO

GA based on the: Erasmus Lump Sum MGA — Multi & Mono - 1.null

PreMETS

Predictive Maintenance Education & Training System: An alliance for boosting the European Innovation in Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial cooperation, education, and training

Project Acronym: **PreMETS**

Project Title: **Predictive Maintenance Education & Training System: An alliance for boosting the European Innovation in Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial cooperation, education, and training**

Project Number: **101108469**

Topic: **ERASMUS-EDU-2022-PI-ALL-INNO-EDU-ENTERP**

Type of Action: **ERASMUS-LS**

[DELIVERABLE TITLE]

[Version]

PreMETS

D[X.Y]: [TITLE]

Deliverable:	
Work Package:	
Due Date:	
Submission Date:	
Start Date of Project:	
Duration of Project:	
Organisation Responsible of Deliverable:	
Version:	
Status:	
Author name(s):	
Reviewer(s):	
Nature:	R – Report P – Prototype D – Demonstrator O - Other
Dissemination level:	PU - Public CO - Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission) RE - Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document history			
Version	Date	Modified by (author/partner)	Comments

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1.1 Purpose of the document.....

1.2 [TITLE]

2 [CHAPTER 2]

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 3.1 [TITLE].....

 3.1.1 [TITLE].....

4 Conclusions.....

5 REFERENCES

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D[X.Y]: [TITLE]

Abbreviations and Terminology

Abbreviations	

Terminology	

Executive Summary

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

1.2

2 [CHAPTER 2]

3 [CHAPTER 3]

3.1 [TITLE]

3.1.1 [TITLE]

4 Conclusions

5 REFERENCES

6 ANNEXES

ANNEX B: INTERNAL REPORTS' CODIFICATION

PreMETS Internal Reports Codification (Document ID):

- First letters: Abbreviated name of the Partner
- Next digits: Number of relevant Task
- Dash
- Next digit: Version number of this report

i.e.: CERTH/HIT1.2_2.DOC : second revision of report in Task 1.2 of CERTH/HIT